

Data FDO Simplified Requirements Version 1.0

22. May 2024

FDO Forum Proposed Endorsement Note 16. June 2024

Reference:

This document is based on the FDO Requirements Specifications as published:

- <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7782262>

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Introduction

This Introduction to the Requirement Specification for Data FDO (FDO-D) focusses on those specifications that were published in the FDO Requirements Specification Document PR3.0 (see reference) relevant for FDOs that contain bit-sequences encoding some useful content (data¹) and their associated metadata². This document deliberately does not cover the full aspects of FDO such as other configurations, types and operations (see [FDO Requirement Specifications](#)), but gives a simplified view of FDO aspects most relevant for data publishing.

Status of this Document

This document is not a full FDO Requirements Specification document, since it only summarizes the full FDP Requirements Specification document for the case of FDOs that have data associated with it. Therefore it can be processed without the many stages according to the FDOF

¹ Data is here meant in the general sense of any bit-sequence, also software could be seen as a bit-sequence.

² There are many other FDO Configuration Types: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7825702>

Process document. It is therefore a Proposed Endorsement Note (PEN) that has been worked out and controlled by FDO TSIG over 3 months and has been endorsed by the FDO Steering Committee.

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1. Background

Most researchers when talking about FDOs have the “canonical” case in mind where FDOs include data. They do not immediately understand, nor need to know, that other possible FDO configurations exist. Consequently, a simplified document specific for this FDO-D configuration which nevertheless is fully compliant with the published full specifications will therefore greatly help engaging and clarifying FDOs with the larger research community.

The FDO-D model in the diagram below describes the core of the specific FDO-D Configuration. The identifier (PID³) resolves to a structured record (FDO-Record) containing a set of attribute-value pairs defined by an FDO-Profile. The types of the attributes must be defined and registered in open registries. The values can include some metadata such as checksum, size, etc. and a set of references that point to the data, metadata, etc. Data and Metadata can reside at different locations. The type of FDO’s content can be used to relate to operations that can be used on the data and are FDOs themselves. The relation between the Content-Type and the possible operations will be maintained by communities of practice.

³ PID in this document stands for a globally unique, resolvable and persistent identifier.

It should be emphasized that

- FDOs are FAIR compliant but do not require FAIRness of the resources at various locations beyond their accessibility, such as the included bit sequences of data and their associated metadata,
- the resolution of the PID resolves to predictable results allowing machines to interpret the attribute-value pairs and to find the resources managed at different locations⁴
- it is assumed that Data FDOs are managed by trustworthy organizations,
- these FDO specifications allow various implementations,
- all crucial terms are defined in the FDO Glossary (indicated in bold face),
- the Type of the content of the FDO (FDO-CT) can be used to relate to operations.

2. FDO-D Requirements

1: Data FAIR Digital Objects (FDO-D) are machine actionable units of information bundling all information that is needed to enable FAIR processing of any included bit-sequence.

2: A **PID**, standing for a globally unique, persistent and resolvable identifier, is assumed to be at the basis for FDOs.

3: A PID resolves to a structured **FDO-Record** compliant with a specified **FDO-Profile** which leads to predictive resolution results.

4: The FDO-Record needs to contain **Mandatory FDO (kernel) Attributes**, may contain **Optional FDO attributes** and attributes agreed upon and defined by recognized communities.

5: Mandatory-FDO-D Attributes are: (1) the **FDO-Content-Type**, (2) the reference to the **FDO-Profile**, (3) the reference to the **bit-sequence(s)** encoding data, (4) the references to the different **metadata** resources⁵.

3. Notes on Requirements

Notes to 1:

- *Relevance: FAIR processing of digital objects is the overall goal and bundling all information into one unit of information is a necessary precondition for this actionability*
- *References point to the included bit-sequences encoding the data and to various types of metadata.*
- *The granularity of FDOs is dependent on pragmatic utility decisions within the communities of practice Those communities define the level of useful entities to use in the corresponding application field.*

Notes to 2:

- *Relevance: A Persistent Identifier is a necessary precondition for findability and accessibility of the unit of information needed for processing.*

⁴ According to the note from Luiz Bonino (ref to come)

⁵ Metadata can be of different sorts, a standardization of terms is required.

- *Every FDO is assigned one or more PIDs.*
- *In accordance with the FAIR principles the protocols to resolve a PID into useful information needs to be standardized, freely accessible, and publicly usable.*

Notes to 3:

- *Relevance: The resolution of the PID is needed to get the unit of information needed for processing and the profile describes the schema for the attributes of this information.*
- *FDO-Records represent the information characterizing the bit-sequence and are resolvable by PIDs, forming the FDO entity..*
- *The term “FDO-Record” is synonymous to the term “PID-Record”.*
- *The PID resolution and the FDO Layer information must be “**machine actionable**”.*

Notes to 4:

- *Relevance: Mandatory and optional FDO attributes are defined by the FDO Forum to increase interoperability. Mandatory attributes must be included in the FDO Profile.*
- *All Attributes need to be defined and registered in open type registries. Values of attributes can be references.*

Notes to 5:

- *Relevance: Data FDOs are a major focus of the specification of FDOs and interoperability is a major concern for this genre. The special choice of the mandatory attributes enables reusability of the whole data FDO, the FDO record by the profile, the data by the FDO-Content-Type and the metadata.*
- *There can be several references to data bit-sequences and to metadata.*